

Integrated Modeling Chain for Tailored Interventions

Insights from the I-CHANGE Project

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Take-Home Messages

Understanding the impact of emission/concentration reduction policies on citizens' mobility behaviour is pivotal for crafting effective strategies. **The use of a numerical modeling chain favours the accurate assessment of policies encompassing various measures**, including incentives for public transportation, traffic restrictions in specific zones, the establishment of infrastructure for bicycles and electric vehicles, and urban planning initiatives aimed at creating pedestrian-friendly environments.

Investing efficiently in mobility strategies, tailored to citizens' needs, can support a durable change of habits that makes the policy effective. **Mobility changes are effective only if the citizens' reactions are sustainable in reducing emissions. It becomes crucial to foster public-private partnerships as well as citizen engagement** to ensure the successful implementation of emission reduction policies and the creation of sustainable urban ecosystems.

Leveraging on a single, yet flexible, methodology, the **Integrated Modeling Chain enables to prioritize the interventions through a consistent and effective evaluation of cost-benefits of different scenarios for the local needs.** ■

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I-CHANGE

Citizen Actions on Climate Change and Environment

I-CHANGE is an Innovation Action project which started in November 2021 and ends in April 2025. It aims to demonstrate how behavioural change of individuals is possible through citizen science initiatives and citizen tailored Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) solutions. I-CHANGE collected environmental and socio-economic data using novel, user-friendly tools such as sensors, monitoring devices, simplified models, and data resources across eight Living Labs. These labs span diverse morphological and geo-climatic conditions, thereby addressing various environmental hazards. The eight I-CHANGE Living Labs are placed in Amsterdam (The Netherlands), Barcelona (Spain), Bologna (Italy), Dublin (Ireland), Genoa (Italy), Hasselt (Belgium), Jerusalem (Israel) and Ouagadougou (Burkina Faso). The promotion of a co-designed learning approach improved citizen knowledge of climate change related to harmful impacts, and helped citizens understand how a behavioural and consumption shift towards sustainable patterns can make a difference.

The usability and interoperability of the collected data has been improved through a dedicated Environmental Impact Hub. ■

The I-CHANGE Integrated Modeling Chain

Involving the active support of citizens in the co-design of fruitful changes to foster the sustainable transition is a first and convincing step to gain the citizens' inclination toward a consistent and durable change of habits, that can be reflected in the entire society and environment. To achieve this general goal, the adoption of (multi)model simulations can serve a twofold result: (i) bring evidence on the efficiency of designed mitigation strategies and (ii) convince the public that mitigation can be pursued, incentivizing the necessary behavioural change it might require. The power of simulation modeling lies in its simplicity and possibility to design reliable scenarios of interventions, overcoming the limitations of observations that are often insufficient to justify the adoption of a specific strategy. However, real-world observations play a crucial role in validating the setup of a simulation model, making it more robust and trustworthy when evaluating potential scenarios. **A validated model or modeling chain yields the alternative scenarios' robust reliability for various mitigation strategies to be unfolded, depending on whether a particular policy or strategic intervention is implemented.** By ensuring this fidelity with real-world systems, decision-makers can confidently explore the implications of their choices through ad-hoc modelling resources.

In the context of the I-CHANGE project, **a set of model simulations has been sequentially performed as an Integrated Modeling Chain** to evaluate the potential mitigation of concentration of CO₂, Greenhouse Gases, Short-Lived Climate Forcers and Air Pollutants, obtained from the implementation of sustainable mobility scenarios, and the consequent behavioural change in different European cities. The integration of these models into the Integrated Modeling Chain allows the assessment of **how mobility-related behaviours can modify the concentrations of various harmful atmospheric compounds in the urban environment.** This procedure ensures the correct integration of each result and the provision of exhaustive information to act upon. ■

The Key Components of the Integrated Modeling Chain are:

- ◆ an Activity-Based Model that can simulate the traffic on the road network based on individual activity-travel schedules and mobility choices;
- ◆ an Emission Model utilized to estimate the release of CO₂, Greenhouse Gases, Short-Lived Climate Forcers and Air Pollutants directly from their urban sources to the atmosphere;
- ◆ a Dispersion Model that is employed to gauge the concentration of CO₂, Greenhouse Gases, Short-Lived Climate Forcers and Air Pollutants at the urban scale.

A visualization of the Integrated Modeling Chain workflow is provided in **Figure 1**.

BASELINE AND POLICY SCENARIOS

Figure 1: I-CHANGE Integrated Modeling Chain workflow. Each triangle depicts the single model (named in capital letters) workflow, with input on the left and output in green. Red arrows link each model with its output, while grey arrows from green boxes highlight outputs from a model that become input for the next in the chain; APs - Air Pollutants; GHGs - Greenhouse Gases, SLCFs - Short-Lived Climate Forcers.

The integration is achieved by combining the output of each model simulation with a set of external additional inputs to set up and run the next model in the chain, enabling to: (i) integrate models from different fields of application within a straightforward workflow, and with that (ii) evaluate the impact of the current mobility regime, and (iii) test scenarios where customized traffic policies are implemented. In both cases of the last two points, the workflow components remain the same. ■

The Model Components and their Workflow in I-CHANGE

The first essential model within the Integrated Modeling Chain is the Activity-Based Model which estimates traffic flows and travel times based on individual trip data. Accounting for both in-home and out-of-home activities, the model generates activity lists and schedules that feed into traffic assignment modeling for refinement. Various data sources, including household travel surveys network skims, land use data, synthetic population data, and network attributes, inform this process ultimately estimating traffic flows. Simulation results are then validated against traffic count data for each city analysed in I-CHANGE before feeding the next model in the chain.

The next step involves the Emission Model that creates an emission inventory by analysing sources of Greenhouse Gas emissions. Outputs from the Activity-Based Model provide critical traffic flow data for this inventory, allowing the assessment of both the current mobility strategy and policy scenarios. Additionally, the model includes inputs related to electricity consumption and waste management to compute the individual carbon and environmental footprints.

Lastly, emission inventories supply data to the Dispersion Model that computes the concentrations of Greenhouse Gases, Short-Lived Climate Forcers and Air Pollutants, factoring in meteorological conditions, topography, morphology, and background pollutant concentrations. Simulation outputs generate concentration maps for the baseline, validated against air quality monitoring data, and different policy scenarios that incorporate the efficacy of traffic-related behavioural changes. This comprehensive approach assesses the interplay between urban policies, traffic patterns, and emissions, making the I-CHANGE Integrated Modeling Chain an adaptable tool for similar evaluations in other regions.

In summary, the I-CHANGE Integrated Modeling Chain offers a robust framework for evaluating the impact of urban policies on traffic flows, travel times, and emissions, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of the dynamics between mobility behaviours and environmental factors. Its adaptability makes it a valuable tool for similar analyses in other regions, provided the necessary data inputs are available. ■

Application of the Workflow

In the initial phase, a standardised format was employed for all input data, encompassing trip/activity data, socio-economic attributes, land-use data, and zonal shape files. Throughout each stage of the simulation process, the baseline scenario was executed, focusing on the mobility patterns of individuals within the population, without any policy influences. Afterwards, validation against real-world data was conducted to ensure accuracy, particularly in consideration of the impact of varying meteorological conditions and examining attributes associated with cold and warm seasons.

Moving to the next phase, the simulation explored the effects of specific policies on population mobility behaviour, employing the established modeling framework. Policy scenarios were tailored based on the region's spatial layout, infrastructure, and socio-economic characteristics. ■

Application Cases with Examples of Emission Reduction Policies

Three I-CHANGE cities, namely **Bologna** in Italy, **Dublin** in Ireland, and **Hasselt** in Belgium were selected for the evaluation of the efficacy of deemed policies for the reduction of Air Pollutants and Greenhouse Gases concentrations. This selection was decided for its representation of different morphological and geo-climatic conditions. The cities vary significantly in size, embodying a metropolitan capital city (Dublin), a medium-sized city (Bologna), and a small-sized city (Hasselt). The selection also spans different climatic bands, encompassing zones from southern to northern and from western to central Europe. While Bologna and Hasselt experience a continental climate, Dublin is influenced by an oceanic climate.

The policy options, developed in collaboration with policymakers and stakeholders in the I-CHANGE Living Labs align with local and regional municipality plans. In Bologna and Dublin, policies focus on enhancing bicycle infrastructure in designated areas (Policy 1) and implementing Low Emission Zones in the city centre (Policy 2). Conversely, in Hasselt, policies involve time-based restrictions on car and private vehicle usage near schools (Policy 3) and promoting flexible working hours/working from home schemes (Policy 4). Specific insights collected from I-CHANGE LLs regarding pre- and post-policy simulation outcomes are described in the following paragraphs. ■

Policy 1: Provision of Bicycle Infrastructure in Designated Areas

To incentivize cycling, the provision of bicycle infrastructures and the enhancement of road safety is tested as a mobility strategy for a sustainable transition. This apportion includes the provision of bike lanes in most of the urban area, while safety is enhanced by limiting vehicle speed. **The expected behavioural change towards a larger adoption of bicycles, instead of motorised solutions, relies on the increased number of roads that the bicyclists can safely use, and on the enhanced time travel imposed by the vehicle speed limits.** The results of Integrated Modeling Chain simulations partially confirm the target behavioural change but also envision an increased public transportation use due to the improved travel time the policy imposes. **The overall impact of the policy is a significant concentration reduction for all Greenhouse Gases, Short-Lived Climate Forcers and Air Pollutants** in most of the urban domain, connected with localised hotspots of increased concentrations. Compared to Policy 2, this mobility strategy applies better to the city of Dublin. ■

Policy 2: Implementation of Low Emission Zones in the Historical City Centre

In accordance with the objectives of the limitation, Low Emission Zones have been implemented worldwide, with numerous variations. The aim of this policy scenario is to strengthen the limitations of the existing Low Emission Zones and mildly expand its spatial coverage to ensure a realistic continuity with existing local regulations. **Results have shown a major change of habits in both the transport modes (public transportation or non-motorized vehicles instead of private cars) and the choices of routes and destinations, increasing the vehicular traffic outside the Low Emission Zones, while decreasing it inside.** The effects on concentration are like those of Policy 1, with a widespread reduction in the whole domain and hotspots in localized areas.

In particular, the traffic redistribution drives increasing concentrations in the road ring around the Low Emission Zones, especially in Bologna, while decreasing external road pollution. Low Emission Zones slightly outperforms bicycle infrastructure in reducing concentrations of Greenhouse Gases, Short-Lived Climate Forcers and Air Pollutants, establishing it as a better solution for the city of Bologna. ■

Policy 3: Time-based Restricted Access to School Streets

The safety of vulnerable people has always been of primary importance to local communities, especially when children are involved. Limiting vehicle access to streets where a school is located during the entry and exit rush is a safety measure for children. It can also grant **co-benefits for the environment, as it triggers a change in the mobility habits** of the families bringing their children to school, and other residents and workers who choose different travel routes to avoid the street closure. In terms of concentration reductions, the overall impact of this policy at the city scale is very limited, especially concerning particulate matters. However, **the concentration reduction of gases such as ozone, carbon dioxide, and nitrogen oxides prove very effective in small areas of the city**, although not necessarily connected with the policy target areas. ■

Policy 4: Flexible/Remote Working Hours

From the urban environmental perspective, working from home has proved a great antidote to air quality problems. The COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated this condition, resulting in a severe abatement of air pollutant concentrations due to the almost complete absence of road traffic emissions for a prolonged time. An adaptive policy mimicking the pandemic situation is that of a flexible working hour schedule with the possibility of home working. **This strategy drastically reduces the morning and evening traffic rushes, but it can produce an increase in the use of private cars for non-working activities.** According to the Integrated Modeling Chain scenario, the **resulting concentrations of Greenhouse Gases, Short-Lived Climate Forcers and Air Pollutants are equally affected by both mobility changes, limiting the overall (positive) impact of this policy.** In the end, the major effect of flexible working hours is to shift activity timings rather than inducing behavioural changes. ■

Conclusion

This policy brief advocates for a holistic approach grounded in the Integrated Modelling Chain, validated within the I-CHANGE Living Labs of Bologna, Dublin and Hasselt, to mitigate CO₂ emissions, Greenhouse Gases, Short-Lived Climate Forcers and Air Pollutants in line with urban sustainability goals. **By evaluating the impact of emission reduction policies on mobility behaviour, cities can chart a course toward sustainable development, and effectively navigate the complexities of urban development, fostering resilient, inclusive, and environmentally conscious communities for both the present and future.** ■

Read More

The content of this brief is based on the following I-CHANGE project reports: “Evaluation framework for the analysis of behavioral changes” (D1.4); “Tools to analyze and evaluate carbon and environmental footprint” (D1.5); “Local implementation plans for each partner city” (D2.2); “Prototype of fully integrated behavioral simulator” (D3.1); “Apportionment of carbon footprint and greenhouse gases” (D3.2); “Apportionment of environmental footprint” (D3.3); “Impact of behavioral changes on CO₂, GHGs, SLCFs, and APs concentrations” (D3.4); “Policy briefs for different policy levels” (D6.8). **All deliverables are available on the I-CHANGE website <https://ichange-project.eu/>.**

Acknowledgment and Disclaimer

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